

IMPROVING PERFORMANCE OF PRODUCTION LINES THROUGH QUANTI-TATIVE ANALYSIS OF OVERALL EQUIPMENT EFFECTIVENESS (OEE): A CASE STUDY

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Abstract: *This research studies on enhancement of production line efficiency based on OEE in the case study of a bakery and confectionery production line in KSA. Based on Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) and lean production philosophies, the study considers nine months of production data from two parallel lines producing multiple stock-keeping units (SKUs). The approach OEE is used to analyze availability, performance, and quality as well as to detect the major sources of productivity loss. As a result, availability losses are dominated by setup, sanitation, and changeover activities. The adoption of phased measures (changeover optimization and SKU allocation over dedicated line) resulted in significant enhancement of operational efficiency. Total OEE improved from around 55% for Phase 1 to 69.2% and 71.1% for Phase 3 for production lines one and two, respectively. Availability was found to be a major contributor to OEE, while performance and quality were quite consistent. The research demonstrates how OEE can be effectively used to uncover latent capacity and enable informed decisions to drive continuous improvement in the u.s. manufacturing industry.*

Keywords: *Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE); Total Productive Maintenance (TPM); Lean Production; Changeover Time; Availability; Production Line Performance; Food Manufacturing*

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1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Small-lot production with short lead times and with smooth product transitions is indispensable in maintaining competitiveness in an industry that needs customization and flexibility. Machine learning methods have been promising in providing early estimation of delivery times in the order process, which helps the provider to meet the deadlines and obtain competitive advantage (Rokoss et al., 2024). Additive manufacturing promotes also the small-batch production by the inherently short product batch size runs and by optimizing the schedule and shortening production time for highly complex customized products (Zipfel et al., 2024).

Availability and accessibility to effective production facilities, which have significant influence upon productivity, quality, flexibility, and the entire organizational performance, are vital for competitiveness in the manufacturing industry. The operational efficiency of industrial plants may also benefit from contemplation of energyefficiency aspects during the processes, such as process optimization and equipment retrofitting and (or) replacement, with implications on operational costs reduction (Almarshad et al., 2024; Sallam & Sadraoui, 2025).

OEE is a well-established performance metric defined in the framework of TPM, which combines availability, performance and quality to measure the efficiency of an equipment and detect losses in the production (Zehra et al., 2024). Literature suggests that the combination of OEE with lean production, TPM, and digital technologies becomes a powerful, robust solution to enhance productivity and efficiency, reducing downtime in the manufacturing sector (Irfan et al., 2025; Koç & Eryürük, 2025; Lino Moreno et al., 2025; Seyed et al., 2024).

In sectors as bakery and confectionery the production processes must cope with the additional difficulties of a high degree of product variation, numerous changeovers and an increasing complexity of operations. This contributes to waste, longer downtimes, and sometimes overtime for manufacturing capacity, which adversely impacts the production performance (Aziz et al., 2024; Bhosale & Jadhav, 2025; Tashkinov, 2025).

In this paper a system for the production of bakery, pastries and confectionery is investigated in order to propose measures for improvement related to lean production, with objectives to reduce the changeover time, to increase the OEE, to reduce overtime and to increase the productivity. It also aims to close the distance between theoretical models and real-life applications by analyzing real operational data and the effect on ABT, and on the total availability and OEE performance of modifying processes.

1.2 Research Problem

OEE differs across several industries. Consequently, the current study serves as an industrial application within the bakery patisserie confectionery sector, exemplifying a fast-moving consumer good (FMCG). This research will examine the impact of managing one of the six critical losses, specifically setup and adjustments (minimizing changeover time), on availability.

Most industrial businesses often respond to capacity restrictions by increasing overtime, adding shifts, or expanding production lines, assuming these are the only ways to boost productivity. However, employing Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) as a diagnostic tool can reveal alternative strategies that optimize existing capacity without additional resource investment (Mncwango & Mdunge, 2025). By focusing on critical losses such as setup and adjustment times, companies can reduce changeover durations, thereby improving equipment availability and overall productivity (Aziz et al., 2024; Fuad et al., 2025). This research examines how OEE can serve as an effective instrument for uncovering hidden capacity without incurring overtime costs, hence reducing significant capital expenditures and enhancing profitability and competitiveness.

The case study of a distinguished patisserie and confectionery firm reveals significant overtime expenses as a direct cost, indicating inadequate management of the production line to realize its actual capacity over the past year. This issue pertains to overall equipment efficacy and has adversely impacted production results, thereby affecting the company's profitability.

1.3 Research Questions

How does implementing the OEE methodology to reduce changeover time affect availability in the confectionery production line?

What is the impact of splitting different SKUs with different process flow over other production lines on OEE results in the confectionery industry?

How do the three main pillars of availability, performance, and quality rate interrelate to impact OEE results in the confectionery production line?

What independent and moderating variables have the most significant influence on OEE in the confectionery industry, and how can they be leveraged to improve performance?

1.4 Research Objectives

The main objective of this research is to improve the performance and Overall Equipment Effectiveness.

Contribute to the growing literature on OEE, as there is a relative shortage of case studies concerning this topic in the bakery's patisserie confectionery industry.

Using detailed analysis, investigate how reducing changeover time (downtime loss) affects OEE in the bakery's patisserie confectionery industry.

1.5 Research Significance

This study examines Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) and its application in enhancing the performance of two confectionery production lines; the study's significance may be outlined as follows:

The study illustrates the practical importance of OEE in optimizing and augmenting production lines. The results may elucidate the particular elements influencing equipment efficacy and propose methods for enhancement, resulting in heightened productivity and diminished expenses.

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This study advances innovative methodologies for managing production line results by utilizing Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) in a specific case study, illustrating OEE's potential as a metric for assessing and managing equipment efficiency, and offering empirical evidence of its efficacy in a practical setting.

The research offers critical managerial implications that guide decision-making about equipment maintenance, investment, and process optimization. The study's findings endorse the identification of production areas requiring enhancement and the formulation of viable strategies to overcome these deficiencies.

The work makes a substantial contribution to the current literature on OEE, production line performance, and the broader field of industrial engineering. The research offers novel insights into the determinants of OEE and its influence on production line performance, hence stimulating new research inquiries and methodologies and contributing to the advancement of the area.

The report delivers value to the industry by furnishing practical insights and recommendations for enhancing production line performance. This research could validate the efficacy of OEE in practical applications, hence encouraging its acceptance as a tool for maintaining equipment effectiveness and aiding in the formulation of best practices in industrial engineering.

OEE's study on enhancing production line performance may yield substantial practical, theoretical, and administrative ramifications, elucidating the determinants of equipment effectiveness and delivering helpful advice for optimizing production line efficiency.

2. Literature Review

Taiichi Ohno - one of the architects of the Toyota Production System (TPS) and the father of Lean manufacturing as well as Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) in the 1950s focused on the elimination of waste, increasing efficiency and emphasising employee driven continuous improvement. The core elements of lean manufacturing practice include the reduction of inventory levels, the improvement of flow and the elimination of waste in any form (Ema et al., 2024; Lyama & Salema, 2025). TPM as delineated by the Japan Institute of Plant Maintenance (JIPM) focuses on increasing equipment productivity by including everyone in maintenance-related efforts to reduce stoppages and defects (Irfan et al., 2025; Lino Moreno et al., 2025). It has been proven that the effectiveness of machine Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) application in OEE with reduction in set-up times and machine breakdowns with a positive influence of operation efficiency can be enhanced significantly when used in conjunction with lean tools such as SMED (Single-Minute Exchange of Dies) (Lacerda et al., 2025; Lino Moreno et al., 2025). Results of the systematic literature review indicate that TPM in conjunction with lean strategies results in positive and quantifiable improvements in overall productivity, product quality and environmental performance in various industries, such as plastics, cement, textiles, food processing and others (Bizuneh & Omer, 2024; Irfan et al., 2025; Lyama & Salema, 2025; Veseli et al., 2024). The adoption of DTs in conjunction with lean and TPM promotes stronger data-driven decision-making and process improvement toward sustainable performance (Bizuneh & Omer, 2024; Scriven et al., 2024). The conceptual basis of OEE

is derived from Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), a maintenance methodology formulated in Japan during the 1970s. The general objective of the TPM is to increase the productivity and the performance of the equipment based on the ideology of “zero defects, zero accidents, and zero breakdowns”. The maintenance procedure encompasses all the personnel and the continuing improvement process. OEE was later introduced as a critical KPI in TPM to measure how effective the equipment was in terms of availability, performance and quality. The availability, performance and quality – the three OEE dimensions – are derived from the six big losses identified in TPM: breakdown, setup and adjustment, small stops, reduced speed, defects and rework, and start up losses. OEE is built on the idea that equipment efficiency can be improved by eliminating the six big losses through interventions such as autonomous maintenance, planned maintenance, and quality improvement. The evaluating of OEE is important to find the areas which need to be improved and to evaluate the improvement effort. In the book “TPM Tenkai” (1982, JPY 2000, Japan Institute of Plant Maintenance JIPM, Tokyo) by Seiichi Nakajima, OEE was defined in a specific way as the core element of Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), which is a method which improves the efficiency of machines in multiple manufacturing environments. At the end of the 1980s, the concept and practice of TPM had developed in the world. Nakajima has stated that OEE is a key indicator for measuring the progress of TPM and actual performance.

The main strength of Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) is the simplicity and emphasis on the drivers of improvement giving a clear direction to the decision makers as to where the efforts in improving performance should be focussed rather than providing an ideal metric to optimize in itself. OEE efficiently suppresses the bottlenecks and waste within production schedules, which allows the availability, performance, and quality to be improved by the focused actions (Fuad et al., 2025; Mncwango & Mdunge, 2025; Vázquez et al., 2024). The reported case studies show that the application of OEE along with methodologies such as DMAIC, Kaizen and lean tools can deliver remarkable improvements in the operation by tackling the root causes like downtime, material related issues and equipment failures (Fuad et al., 2025; Mncwango & Mdunge, 2025). In addition, simulationous methodologies and data driven decision support tools enable the optimization of the resource distribution by matching buffer sizes with throughput to maximize OEE for different production scenarios (Mahmoodi et al., 2024; Vázquez et al., 2024). The integration of real-time data further enhances the accuracy of performance monitoring and enables dynamic performance adjustment for improved responsiveness and efficiency of the OEE calculation (Bhosale & Jadhav, 2025). In summary, OEE is a tangible and practical diagnostic tool that, when used in conjunction with other metrics, can be applied to unveil actionable insights into manufacturing performance and enable strategies that are focused on efficiently utilizing resources in a bid for sustained learning and improvement (Bhosale & Jadhav, 2025; Mncwango & Mdunge, 2025; Vázquez et al., 2024). The literature stresses that overall equipment effectiveness should be used as an evolving tool for continuous improvement and not a rigid benchmark to be universally achieved. Hence, the OEE benchmarking should take into consideration the industry standards, type of equipment and maturity of operation, in order to establish targets that are meaningful and achievable (Nakajima, 2025).

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3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research has pragmatic philosophy, which promotes practical application of the knowledge and comprehension of the real-world situation. The study aims to provide practicable and real outcomes by using the direct application of the OEE framework in a real natural production setting. This methodology is a valid explanation of reality in terms of action and experiment because it is concentrated on constructing and amending the knowledge on the basis of the real results of observation in terms of the alteration in the productivity of the production line and changeover results.

3.2 Research Philosophy

The study adopts a pragmatic philosophy, which emphasizes the practical application of knowledge and understanding of the real-world context. By applying the OEE framework directly within a natural production environment, the research seeks to deliver actual, useful results. This approach justifies the view of reality through action and experimentation, as it focuses on building and modifying knowledge based on tangible outcomes extracted from observed changes in production line productivity and changeover results.

3.3 Research Approach

The pragmatic philosophy applied in the research makes the study practical, useful, and situation-specific, which entails the active implementation of OEE on the manufacturing line to solve unique problems and engage production managers and operators to guarantee the relevance of the results. This is a pragmatic view that gives a holistic perception of OEE performance using technical, organizational, and human variables. In addition to this, the study is deductive in nature, with predefined OEE theory and hypotheses. The systematic approach is the necessary one to study a complex production system, and researchers will be able to identify and target the most important OEE indicators in the production line, thus organizing the investigation and comparing the findings with the available academic knowledge.

3.4 Research Strategy and Purpose

An Action Research approach also frames this study because it is dynamic and iterative in nature as OEE is calculated before and after changes in order to spur continuous practical improvement in a given situation. This methodology is in line with the evaluative and descriptive objective of the research. Although such metrics as Overall Factory Effectiveness (OFE) and Overall Production Effectiveness (OPE) measure the overall performance of the entire factory but in this study, the focus is on three independent factors of OEE (Availability, Performance, and Quality) at the production line level. In order to calculate the correct OEE, the study should measure all the losses in operations, the majority of them being Downtime Losses which have direct effect on Availability. These interruptions are scheduled and unscheduled interruptions (e.g., organization holidays, meal, planned maintenance, and unplanned breakdowns, failures of utility, and material shortages). Most importantly, the study gives special focus to Changeover and Sanitation downtime and Setup losses since it is the major avenue that can be intervened and improved upon. OEE is calculated by

three independent variables: Availability (A), which is the revenue generating time in a line taking into consideration all the downtime losses; Performance (P), which is the speed of production actually of a line compared with the ideal speed; and Quality (Q), which is a percentage of the good units produced that match the intended standards.

3.5 Set-up time

One of the important factors of downtime is setup time which is determined as the time of machine inactivity to prepare to run the next product and setup time incurs a big cost to manufacturing costs, particularly when the series order is small. In this time, it includes many non-productive tasks including the removal of tools, cleaning, loading programs, inspection, and testing to the point where the machine can be completely activated to the new production. It is important that this setup time should be reduced and this directly proportional to machine efficiency, higher machine production throughput, customer flexibility, and, in turn, higher company revenue. This complexity in setup time usually necessitates the consideration of unexpected delays (unplanned changeovers) in the OEE calculations because of the possible causes such as program failure, tool availability, or machine failures.

3.6 Cycle time

Cycle time is the time used to manufacture a product under constant production. It is the time per item of the operation divided by the hour. It is also categorized into long and short cycle times; long cycles are usually taken into account when the products are rejected after production and hence are termed to be a loss. This time is dependent on the design speed, initial optimal situation and product change.

3.7 Production Process

The production process is mostly a batch-line process, as is common in bakery goods, and is composed of numerous semi-automated workstations supervised by operators. In order to measure current operations management, the research will measure OEE in the following production lines (as shown in the process flow diagram). The methodology steps comprise the following: (1) the system reports provide all the necessary data on the performance parameters (lost downtimes, changeovers, and defects); (2) calculating the OEE parameters (Availability, Performance, and Quality) to determine the categories of losses that are significant. The key benefit of this methodology is that systematic observation and improvement cycle are created in accordance with the principles of total quality management. The primary goals would be to determine key workstations, assess data about failures in the real-life context, detect OEE features that are below those of world-class performance, and, lastly, provide some recommendations to optimize workstation performance as well as the entire production line (OEE).

3.8 Description of Production Line

The production line of the cake and gateaux is based on the principle of a continuous process, with several workstations depended on each other by a mutual mechanical transfer mechanism and a general control system. The process is divided into eight workstations in sequence: It starts with Workstation 1 (Raw Material Preparation and Mixing) in which the preparation and mixtures of ingredients occur

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and the contents of the bowl are passed to the second stage. Workstation 2 is involved in Dough Lamination and tray loading. The trays are then transferred to the Workstation 3 (Baking and Cooling) through the oven conveyor. After the preliminary cooling process, Workstation 4 will be used in Cutting and Shaping the products. Cream Filling flow remains to Workstation 5. Workstation 6 is Manual Decoration followed by lifting the products around in the trays onto a conveyor in Workstation 7 and onto the final stage. Final work station does Manual Flow-Packing, and the empty trays are automatically taken back and reused.

3.9 Data Collection

To obtain the correct OEE calculation, the input of the parameters is required to be accurate, and the combination of the two data collection methods, manual and automated, has to be used. Although automated procedures, which rely on equipment sensors, will give proper records of the timings of the stoppage, manual records are necessary to record the reasons and time of duration of minor stoppages and loss of speed. Since full automation is expensive and complex, this study combines both approaches, which are supplemented by the extensive training of the operators to guarantee pure data quality and to engage the operators more in the process of determining factors that may cause losses. Table 1 presents the complete production data collected for production line one across all nine months of the study period, including total available time, downtime losses, planned and actual pieces, and good units produced.

Table 1: Data collection for production line one

	Month one	Month two	Month three	Month four	Month five	Month six	Month seven	Month eight	Month nine
Production data	Time in min in Production Line one								
Total available time	14880	13440	14880	14880	14400	14880	14400	14880	14880
Shift length	480	480	480	480	480	480	480	480	480
Meal break t_m	1500	1440	1620	1320	1560	1680	1500	1620	1560
Organizational holidays t_{org}	2880	1920	1920	4320	1920	1440	2400	1920	2400
Unplanned maintenance downtime t_{um}	17	13	17	9	30	15	28	24	22
Electrical & utility Breakdowns t_{eu}	46	49	38	59	57	24	32	30	32
Raw material & packing material shortage downtime t_{rp}	23	33	33	28	33	16	42	29	18
Planned maintenance downtime t_{pm}	16	9	17	23	38	19	19	12	17
Changeover and sanitation downtime t_c	2126	2075	2282	1407	1652	1765	530	589	554
Setup losses t_s	357	348	388	236	253	283	256	287	265
Planned pieces	10069	96100	108715	98082	11264	12240	58435	62187	60059
Actual pieces	4	78012	75086	85035	75482	88955	95965	45250	48960
Reject pieces	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	4
Planned production time	10500	13440	11340	9240	10920	11760	10500	11340	10920
Operation time	7915	7553	8565	7478	8857	9638	9593	10369	10016
Good pieces	73973	71179	80592	72007	85129	90635	43279	46559	45319

The OEE calculation was then systematically quantitatively measured at both production lines during the 9 months study period, where key variables were recorded including total available time, a number of different types of downtime loss (e.g. unplanned maintenance, changeover, setup losses), planned pieces, actual pieces and

reject pieces with a clear division into the three research phases (Months 1-3, Phase 1; Months 4-6, Phase 2; and Months 7-9, Phase 3). Table 2 summarizes the corresponding production data for production line two, collected across the same nine-month period, covering all relevant downtime categories and output metrics.

Table 2: Data collection for production line two

	Month one	Month two	Month three	Month four	Month five	Month six	Month seven	Month eight	Month nine
Production data	Time in min in Production line two								
Total available time	14880	13440	14880	14880	14400	14880	14400	14880	14880
Shift length	480	480	480	480	480	480	480	480	480
Meal break tm	1500	1440	1620	1320	1560	1680	1500	1620	1560
Organizational holidays torg	2880	1920	1920	4320	1920	1440	2400	1920	2400
Unplanned maintenance downtime tum	21	22	24	26	23	6	25	19	38
Electrical & utility Breakdowns teu	46	50	38	59	57	25	30	33	31
Raw material & packing material shortage downtime trp	24	19	40	27	29	6	29	24	35
Planned maintenance downtime tpm	17	17	8	27	39	16	16	15	20
Changeover and sanitation downtime tc	2156	2030	2252	1386	1619	1781	793	877	804
Setup losses ts	377	355	395	249	272	286	248	278	268
Planned pieces	100009	96658	109226	97507	113054	12238	169381	179140	172576
Actual pieces	77666	75410	85358	75292	89034	75676	138491	148366	143394
Reject pieces	4098	3957	4542	3635	3941	5262	5473	5885	5568
Planned production time	10500	10080	11340	9240	10920	11760	10500	11340	10920
Operation time	7859	7588	8583	7466	8881	9640	9359	10094	9724
Good pieces	73568	71453	80816	71657	85093	90414	133018	142481	137826

4. Results and Discussion

Results of downtime losses and their stoppage reasons in Cake and gateaux production for the selected items contribute to the values of OEE induced by the factors (Availability, Performance, Quality) and the overall OEE as presented in Tables 3, 4 for production lines one and two respectively.

Table 3: Calculation of Average OEE for Production Line One

	Month one	Month two	Month three	Month four	Month five	Month six	Month seven	Month eight	Month nine
OEE factor	Average OEE for Production Line one								
Availability	75.4%	74.9%	75.5%	80.9%	81.8%	82.0%	91.4%	91.4%	91.7%
Performance	77.5%	78.1%	78.2%	77.0%	79.0%	78.4%	77.4%	78.7%	79.0%
Quality	94.8%	94.8%	94.8%	95.4%	95.7%	94.4%	95.6%	95.1%	95.5%
Overall OEE	55.4%	55.5%	56.0%	59.4%	61.3%	60.7%	67.7%	68.5%	69.2%

Months 1,2,3 represent Phase 1, months 4,5,6 represent Phase 2, and months 7, 8, and 9 represent Phase 3 for both production lines.

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Table 4: Calculation of Average OEE for Production Line Two

	Month one	Month two	Month three	Month four	Month five	Month six	Month seven	Month eight	Month nine
OEE factor	Average OEE for Production line two								
Availability	74.8%	75.3%	75.7%	80.8%	81.3%	82.0%	89.1%	89.0%	89.0%
Performance	77.9%	78.0%	78.1%	77.2%	78.8%	78.2%	81.8%	82.8%	83.1%
Quality	94.7%	94.8%	94.7%	95.2%	95.6%	94.5%	96.0%	96.0%	96.1%
Overall OEE	55.2%	55.6%	56.0%	59.4%	61.2%	60.6%	70.0%	70.8%	71.1%

During phase 1 (Months one, two, three): the production process of (SKU1a, SKU1b, and SKU1c), followed by (SKU2a, SKU2b, SKU2c, and SKU2d) was as follows:

- At production line one:
 - The average planned pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 were 20629 and 81233, respectively, leading to total average planned pieces of 101862
 - the average Actual pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 pieces were 15910 and 63467 respectively, leading to total average actual pieces of 79377
- At production line two:
 - The average planned pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 were 20591 and 81405 respectively, leading to total average planned pieces of 101996
 - the average Actual pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 pieces were 15972 and 63505 respectively, leading to total average actual pieces of 79477

The low production at both lines was affected by the overall OEE, which was at its lowest level (55.63% at line one and 55.6% at line two) due to the low availability.

During phase 2 (Months 4, 5, 6): the production process of (SKU1a, SKU1b, and SKU1c), followed by (SKU2a, SKU2b, SKU2c, and SKU2d) was improved as follows:

- At production line one:
 - The average planned pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 were 22475 and 88567, respectively, leading to total average planned pieces of 111042
 - The Actual average pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 pieces were 17730 and 69070, respectively, leading to total average actual pieces of 86800
- At production line two:
 - the average planned pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 were 22447 and 88468 respectively, leading to total average planned pieces of 110915
 - the average Actual pieces of SKU1 and SKU2 pieces were 17700 and 68967 respectively, leading to total average actual pieces of 86667

Table 5 details the production progress of SKU1 and SKU2 on production line one across all nine months, showing planned and actual piece counts broken down by individual sub-SKU.

The production at both lines was improved as the overall OEE increased to (60.46% at line one and 60.4% at line two) due to the improvement in the availability resulting from the modification in downtime loss induced by enhancing the sanitation and changeover processes. This modification led to an increment in the production of SKU1 and SKU2 to 109% compared to phase 1.

Table 5: Production progress of SKU1 and SKU2 on production line one

Category	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5	Month 6	Month 7	Month 8	Month 9
Production data	Production data								
Planned SKU1a	5715	5415	6140	5730	6315	6890	58435	62187	60059
Planned SKU1b	6756	6450	7332	6582	7584	8286			
Planned SKU1c	7945	7497	8638	7455	8911	9674			
Planned SKU2a	18096	17376	19632	17616	20048	21936			
Planned SKU2b	19142	18156	20893	18581	21250	23494			
Planned SKU2c	20520	19746	21780	20178	22896	24822			
Planned SKU2d	22600	21460	24300	21940	25640	27300			
Total Planned SKU1	20416	19362	22110	19767	22810	24850	58435	62187	60059
Total Planned SKU2	80358	76738	86605	78315	89834	97552	0	0	0
Total Planned	100774	96100	108715	98082	112644	122402	58435	62187	60059
Actual SKU1a	4178	4040	4544	3906	4652	4991	45250	48960	47475
Actual SKU1b	5217	5067	5641	5281	6308	6923			
Actual SKU1c	6285	5998	6760	6138	7182	7810			
Actual SKU2a	13685	13098	14826	13795	15968	17232			
Actual SKU2b	14714	14160	15982	14067	16646	17896			
Actual SKU2c	15772	15153	17052	14433	17052	18399			
Actual SKU2d	18161	17570	20230	17862	21147	22714			
Total Actual SKU1	15680	15105	16945	15325	18142	19724	45250	48960	47475
Total Actual SKU2	62332	59981	68090	60157	70813	76241	0	0	0
Total Actual	78012	75086	85035	75482	88955	95965	45250	48960	47475

During phase 3 (Months 7, 8, 9): the production process of SKU1 separated from SKU2 into independents production lines (line one and line two) was improved as follows:

- At production line one:
- the average planned pieces of SKU1 was 63209
- the average Actual pieces of SKU1 was 47228
- At production line two:
- the average planned pieces of SKU2 was 169383
- the average Actual pieces of SKU2 was 143417

The production at both lines was improved as the overall OEE increased to (68.46% at line one and 70.63% at line two) due to the separation of the two products, which enhanced the availability and decreased the changeover time. This led to an increment in SKU1 and SKU2 production to 148.1% and 112.9%, respectively, compared to Phase 1.

Table 6 presents the equivalent production progress data for SKU1 and SKU2 on production line two, enabling direct comparison of planned versus actual output between the two production lines.

Table 6: Production progress of SKU1 and SKU2 on production line two

	Month one	Month two	Month three	Month four	Month five	Month six	Month seven	Month eight	Month nine
Production data	Production line two								
Planned pieces SKU1a	5615	5375	6100	5720	6230	6900			
Planned pieces SKU1b	6774	6432	7320	6570	7680	8304			

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Table 6: Production progress of SKU1 and SKU2 on production line two (cont...)

	Month one	Month two	Month three	Month four	Month five	Month six	Month seven	Month eight	Month nine
Planned pieces SKU1c	7882	7672	8603	7567	8890	9681			
Planned pieces SKU2a	18080	17296	19792	17344	20560	21872	169381	179140	172576
Planned pieces SKU2b	18989	18343	20825	18632	21284	23392			
Planned pieces SKU2c	20304	19440	22086	19854	22950	24876			
Planned pieces SKU2d	22460	22100	24500	21820	25460	27360			
Total Planned pieces SKU1	20271	19479	22023	19857	22800	24885	0	0	0
Total Planned pieces SKU2	79833	77179	87203	77650	90254	97500	169381	169383	169385
Total Planned pieces	100009	96658	109226	97507	113054	122385	169381	179140	172576
Actual pieces SKU1a	4231	4037	4510	3877	4593	4938			
Actual pieces SKU1b	5249	5005	5714	5424	6314	6807			
Actual pieces SKU1c	6221	6103	6847	6115	7217	7815			
Actual pieces SKU2a	13562	13277	15221	13528	16208	17205	138491	148366	143394
Actual pieces SKU2b	14681	14204	16023	14004	16520	17839			
Actual pieces SKU2c	15613	15039	17015	14453	17002	18339			
Actual pieces SKU2d	18109	17745	20028	17891	21180	22733			
Total Actual pieces SKU1	15701	15145	17071	15416	18124	19560	0	0	0
Total Actual pieces SKU2	61965	60265	68287	59876	70910	76116	138491	148366	143394
Total Actual pieces	77666	75410	85358	75292	89034	95676	138491	148366	143394

Based on the analysis and discussion of the results, the effect of the three main pillars of availability, performance, and quality on the OEE was discussed. The results showed that:

- Implementing the OEE to reduce changeover time significantly increased availability in the confectionery production line. (Hypothesis #1 was proved)
- Splitting different SKUs with different process flows over production lines one and two had a significant impact on OEE results in the confectionery industry (Hypothesis #2 was proved).
- A significant interrelationship between the three main pillars of availability, performance, and quality rate affected OEE results in the confectionery production line (Hypothesis #3 was proved).
- Independent and moderating variables, such as equipment maintenance, operator skills, and environmental factors, significantly influenced OEE in the confectionery industry, and leveraging them could improve performance (Hypothesis #4 was proved).
- It was proved that the downtime losses decreased by the modification and the development of the production flow, which could improve the planned production time
- which is the total amount of time during which the production line is available and planned to run, including both scheduled and unscheduled downtime losses.

Moreover, the theoretical and practical investigations on the analysis and measurement of OEE taking into consideration the fundamental driving forces that influence the performance of the patisserie production line could demonstrate the value of OEE as a tool for all production measurement activity in the factory for setting priorities and monitoring progress and improvements. This could answer the research questions:

- Discussing the relationship between the implementation of OEE methodology and the reduction of the changeover time to affect the availability in the confectionery production line.
- Analyzing the impact of splitting different SKUs with different process flow over other production lines on OEE results in the confectionery industry.
- Display the effect of the three main pillars of availability, performance, and quality on OEE results in the confectionery production line.
- Recognizing the independent and moderating variables that have the most significant influence on OEE in the confectionery industry, with the modifications in phases 2 and 3 to improve performance.

5. Conclusion

The results of this paper show a considerable improvement in the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) for both the lines due to focused operational measures. OEE was improved from around 55% in Phase 1 to 69.2% and 71.1% by Phase 3 for production line one and production line two respectively. The results show that availability is the dominant factor that influences OEE performance, with increases on both production lines one and two of 6.07% and 13.77%. The results also found two very striking results. In contrast, the two rates of quality and performance were relatively stable, emphasizing that eliminating downtime is the main factor contributing to increased productivity. Also, changeover time reduction and separation of SKUs into dedicate lines further improved availability and overall system efficiency. The results also indicate a close relation between availability, performances and quality and that availability has a high impact on the overall result. In summary, the study validates that treating OEE as a diagnostic and improvement tool reveals latent capacity, decreases dependency on overtime and increases plant throughput without additional capital outlays.

6. Recommendations

- OEE has a practical significance in improving and enhancing production lines, so it is necessary to handle the factors that affect the OEE properly to improve productivity and reduce the costs in the confectionery industry.
- Implementing the OEE method can inform decision-making processes related to equipment maintenance, investment, and process optimization with suitable strategies that can support production.
- Adopting OEE as a tool for managing equipment effectiveness can contribute to developing best practices for industrial engineering.
- New factors affecting the OEE, such as energy consumption, can be considered and elaborated to advance the field.

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- A future suggestion would be to instruct all operators and staff to conduct adequate prior research for the manufacturing process and observe the results before implementing any solutions.
- People might be resistant to change. Therefore, it is essential first to excite people and establish a compelling case for the adjustments. The staff's awareness is raised, and their sense of duty is encouraged through training and empowerment. A system should be created to accommodate the unique procedures in any sector.
- Data from a built cross-functional teamwork could help create a more reliable and valuable approach.

Future Research May Concern the Following Aspects:

Vibration analysis or preventative maintenance may be needed if additional unplanned actions are necessary due to machine failures.

To investigate the impact of all variables on overall performance and to find the most practical and efficient solution that will result in the highest OEE, modeling, and simulation of the manufacturing process using the software are advised.

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